

Fabrication of a W-Band Sheet Beam Extended Interaction Klystron (EIK)*

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Abstract: A W-band sheet-beam extended interaction klystron (EIK) is being fabricated and integrated with our previously demonstrated 19.5-kV, 3.3-A beamstick. The EIK is predicted by 3-D particle-in-cell simulations to have a saturated output power of almost 10 kW and a small-signal gain >40 dB. Key design features of the device will be reviewed, and the status of the fabrication and testing will be discussed.

Keywords: Sheet beam; EIK; millimeter wave; vacuum electronic; amplifier; MAGIC; ICEPIC.

Introduction

To demonstrate the significant increase in power that can be achieved at a given operating voltage by substituting a sheet beam for a pencil beam, we are developing a sheet-beam extended interaction klystron at ~94 GHz. We have shown that a sheet beam EIK is attractive because of its high gain per unit length, simple topology, and capacity for relatively high power [1]. Our EIK employs a permanent magnet solenoid that produces a field of 8.5 kG, allowing operation at a relatively low voltage of 19.5 kV.[2] A beamstick has been fabricated and tested, successfully transporting the 0.32 x 4 mm, 3.3-A beam from the cathode to a depressed collector with >98% efficiency.[3] Here, we will present results from the full amplifier design and fabrication and discuss the status of our research.

Baseline Performance

The layout of the EIK is shown in Figure 1. The circuit consists of identical 5-gap input, output, and buncher cavities. A 5 mm x 0.4 mm beam tunnel passes through the cavities. A slightly ramped magnetic field, which increases from 7.6 to 8.6 kG over a distance of 2.8 cm, is supplied by a permanent magnet. The individual gaps in each cavity are strongly coupled by coupling cavities on both sides of the beam tunnel, and power is injected into and extracted from the device via WR-10 waveguides attached to the cavities through rectangular apertures. The buncher cavity is externally loaded to provide the optimum Q . Initial simulations [1] of the EIK were performed with MAGIC-3D (ATK/Mission Systems), while most of the simulations performed for the final design and optimization were per-

Figure 1. EIK topology. Total length is 2.2 cm.

With perfect alignment and tuning, simulations indicate the amplifier is stable. However, the rectangular beam tunnel is not cut off to the fundamental TE_{10} mode at the operating frequency, and slight misalignment of the circuit or small fabrication errors can cause this mode to be excited, resulting in circuit oscillation. Consequently, the circuit also incorporates $\lambda/4$ chokes, as shown in Fig. 1, which ICEPIC simulations have shown to be quite effective at reducing coupling between the cavities due to misalignment or fabrication errors.[4] However, even with these chokes, only very small misalignments (on the order of 25 μ m) can be tolerated due to excitation of unwanted modes in the individual cavities. The sensitivity to these misalignments is also significantly greater in the higher gain 3-cavity circuit than in the 2-cavity version we initially studied.[1,4] A key goal of the development effort is to demonstrate that these potential problems can be overcome in a high-gain, high-power circuit. The simulations indicate this is possible with tightly controlled tolerances.

The EIK operates in the 2π TM_{01} -like mode, with gaps spaced for synchronism with a 19.5 kV beam (0.78 mm period). Gap, coupling cavity, and waveguide aperture dimensions are carefully selected to maximize interaction impedance (R/Q), to provide good field uniformity across the full beam width, and to space undesirable modes as far as possible from the operating mode. Figure 2 depicts an HFSS (Ansoft LLC) simulation in which power is coupled from the waveguide at the resonant frequency. Excellent field uniformity is achieved, both across the beam width and from one gap to the next. By integrating the electric field along multiple z-directed lines in the cavity midplane, we find that R/Q ranges from about 43 Ω to 51 Ω .

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Figure 2. (a) $|E|$ in midplane. (b) E_z vs. z in midplane at $x = 0, \pm 1$ mm.

Gain curves for both 2-cavity and 3-cavity versions of this EIK, as computed by ICEPIC, are shown in Fig. 3. In both cases, the output saturates at just under 10 kW. To achieve the higher gain, the 3-cavity version was selected for fabrication, even though this required lengthening the uniform magnetic field region by about 1 cm from the value used in the beamstick. In the simulations, the cavities are all identical. In the actual device, tuners are incorporated into the coupling cavities to allow fine tuning of the resonant frequencies.

Figure 3. Output power and gain vs. drive power for 2-cavity and 3-cavity versions of the EIK.

EIK Circuit

Final design of the circuit was based on simulations that addressed issues such as cavity spacing, coupling iris size and shape, and choke configuration. Results of these simulations will be summarized. The 3-cavity circuit was subsequently fabricated and cold tested, with performance very close to the design parameters.

Fabrication and assembly of the full amplifier are underway, and preliminary results and program status will be discussed. A solid model of the assembly is shown in Fig. 4.

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Figure 4. Solid model of W-band EIK.

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